

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 3

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№3 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2024-3>

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ISSN: 2181-9297

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FRANZ BOAS, EDWARD SAPIR AND LEONARD BLOOMFIELD AS FOUNDERS OF AMERICAN STRUCTURALISM

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13235201>

ABSTRACT

In this article, the basic principles of American structuralism and its application in various fields such as linguistics, cultural anthropology and literature are discussed. Structuralism is one of the important trends in modern linguistics and studies language as a system of signs and rules. The criticism of American structuralism and its influence on modern research is also considered. In addition, it tells about the life and work of great linguists such as Franz Boas, Edward Sapir and Leonard Bloomfield.

Key words: structuralism, descriptivism, views, anthropology, modern linguistics, criticism, research, psycholinguistics, scientific, symbols, signs etc.

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FRANS BOAS, EDUARD SEPIR VA LEONARD BLUMFILD AMERIKA STRUKTURALIZMINING ASOSCHILARI SIFATIDA

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Amerika strukturalizmining asosiy tamoyillari va uning tilshunoslik, madaniy antropologiya va adabiyot kabi turli sohalarda qo'llanilishi muhokama qilinadi. Strukturalizm zamonaviy tilshunoslikning muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, tilni belgilar va qoidalar tizimi sifatida o'rganadi. Amerika strukturalizmining tanqidi va uning zamonaviy tadqiqotlarga ta'siri ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, u Frans Boas, Edvard Sapir va Leonard Blumfild kabi buyuk tilshunoslarning hayoti va ijodi haqida hikoya qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: strukturalizm, deskriptivizm, qarashlar, antropologiya, zamonaviy tilshunoslik, tanqid, tadqiqot, psixolingvistika, ilmiy, ramzlar, belgilar va boshqalar.

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ФРАНЦ БОАС, ЭДВАРД СЕПИР И ЛЕОНАРД БЛУМФИЛД КАК ОСНОВАТЕЛИ АМЕРИКАНСКОГО СТРУКТУРАЛИЗМА**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В этой статье обсуждаются основные принципы американского структурализма и его применение в различных областях, таких как лингвистика, культурная антропология и литература. Структурализм является одним из важных направлений современной лингвистики, изучающей язык как систему знаков и правил. Также рассматривается критика американского структурализма и его влияние на современные исследования. Кроме того, он рассказывает о жизни и творчестве таких великих лингвистов, как Франц Боас, Эдвард Сепир и Леонард Блумфилд.

Ключевые слова: структурализм, дескриптивизм, взгляды, антропология, современное языкознание, критика, исследования, психолингвистика, научность, символы, знаки и т.д.

American structuralism is a linguistic school that developed in the United States in the mid-20th century. It based on the ideas of European structuralism, but has its own characteristics and accents. The basic principle of American structuralism is a systematic analysis to the study of language and culture. It suggests that language and culture are composed of elements that interact and form complex systems. These elements can be sounds, words, grammatical rules, symbols, etc.

The system of language and culture is emphasized by American structuralism. It examines how the elements of language and culture are organized and how they function within a system. For example, in linguistics, members of structuralism evaluate the phonological structure of a language's sound inventory and the grammatical rules that determine the order of words in a sentence[2.45].

American structuralism also actively uses semiotics - the science of signs and symbols. It explores how signs and symbols are used to convey information and create meaning. For example, in literature, members of structuralism evaluate how literary texts use symbols and metaphors to convey certain ideas and emotions.

There are three main schools of structuralism in the present era, named Prague Structuralism, American Structuralism and Copenhagen structuralism.

Prague structuralism

The same structuralism is in general linguistics also known as functional linguistics. Language based on what this school calls functional linguistics. Representatives of the school of functional linguistics: V. Matezius, B. Trnka, I. Vahek, B. Gavranek, N.S. Trubetskoi, R.O. Jakobson, S.I. Kartsevsky and others.

The basic ideas of the teaching of the Prague school are as follows:

1. Linguistics is an independent science with its own object.
2. Language is a system.
3. Language is a functional system, that is, language is directed to a specific purpose is a system of means of expression.
4. Phonology - theoretical phonology.
5. Synchrony and diachrony. Prague members of structuralism study language they mainly promote synchronicity - the synchronous method. So, synchrony and diachrony are taken as dialectically related in the analysis of language - language phenomena, units.
6. A word with a language symbol is an independent unit.
7. The morpheme maintains the language's morphological structure.
8. The question of actual division of the sentence, etc[5.100].

American Structuralism

American structuralism is a linguistic school that developed in the United States in the mid-20th century. It came to the field as a result of learning the language of the local population. The founder of this school is an American famous ethnographer, anthropologist and linguist Franz Boas (1858 –1942)

Many of the grammatical characteristics of various American local languages described by Boas and his supporters are still more successfully used today to eliminate all linguistic prejudices, any familiar and tainted by affiliation with a specific scientific school of thought, any attempts to assign classifications that occur in European languages, and languages that are apprehensive and uncommon from our point of view.

Already in his initial linguistic developments ("On alternating sounds", 1889), Boas attempts to establish that each individual assesses sounds an unfamiliar language through the sounds of his native dialect, and thus, when documenting semantics, we must regularly free ourselves from mistakes with transcriptions coming from the structures of our native language [7.87]. F. Boas did not look for general rules outside of the historical accounts, as though synchronicity was just a simple case of particular phenomena happening at the same time.

However, he was extremely dissatisfied in his quest for general principles clarifying historical sequences, forms of culture, and, especially particular, the evolution of language: although linguistic data contain many remarkably comparable phenomena from a wide variety of corners of the world, they demonstrate their autonomous beginnings and therefore, any attempt to bring them under a single foundation turns out to be unsuccessful.

Comparable structures can grow in a variety of ways and climb via various routes to various sources. Structure similarity does not indicate development similarity. Moreover, when this discrepancy becomes clearer, search for laws of development of language (and social life in general) for Boas becomes less useful and more hopeless[4.98-99].

Sapir was born on January 26, 1884 in Germany. His father emigrated to America in 1889. While still a student, Sapir conducted field research on the Chinook-Wishram language and the Takelma language (on which he would write and defend his doctoral dissertation); during the first time after his studies, he studied the Java language and the Paiute language. On Boas' recommendation, he is given a position as head of the anthropology department at the Geological Survey of the National Museum in Ottawa, where he moves and starts a family.

Working in Canada was an opportunity to gain financial independence to continue conducting field research. He makes long trips to Vancouver Island to visit the Nootka Indians, collecting material on various Indian languages. This period of Sapir's life occupies a significant place in his biography, since it was then that he formed his research method and his theory[3.35]. At the same moment, he wrote the book "Language," which immediately attracted the attention of the public and nominated him among the leading theorists.

E. Sapir identifies and describes social differences in the Indian language that seem exotic to speakers of modern European languages. For example, in the Yao language (Northern California), a scientist found that there are significant phonetic and grammatical differences between the male and female versions of speech, surprisingly, this language does not have a gender category.

American linguist E. Sapir created many studies on linguistic typology, ethnology and cultural problems. His more than 200 works on the study of Indian languages are of great value in the study of general linguistics and linguistic cultures in North America.

For most of his career, Sapir held positions in the department of anthropology, which successfully influenced his worldview: he perceived language as a phenomenon interconnected with other external spheres of life, and not as an element removed from the world.

Died due to heart disease at 55 years old. As Sapir's widow wrote, the scientist felt that his strength was fading, in recent years he was no longer so energetic and regretted that he did not have time to find out and tell everything. However, languages remained his passion throughout his life. He has written more than 200 scientific papers, some of which are still awaiting their first publication.

Taking into account the connection between thought and language, Sapir says that thinking is the greatest possible level of speech content in terms of language. In actuality, the communication circumstance affects the internal substance, intensity, and mental significance of speech. [8.123]. Because of this, the strict definitions of language and thought do not coincide. Language is not a "label" that is applied to a preconceived notion, and the idea that one can reason and think without language is false.

Comparing two images in figurative thinking already entails a "silent" flow of language. In his later work, Sapir presents his theory of the nature and purposes of language in the essay "Language" (Sapir, 1993b). Here, the perfection and universality of language as a communication [9.298]. Because language can symbolically represent reality and experience, it is believed to be the basis of all human functions, including behavioral, psychological, and communicative ones. This argument is based on the clause that states that linguistic elements have a symbolic aspect that begins at the phoneme, or sound, level.

Language plays a crucial function in the accumulation and historical transmission of culture and is an essential component of our conscious activities. It is the most important element in a person's development of identity and simultaneously a potent socializing and uniting force:

“Human language habits are very significant as unconscious indicators of the most significant traits of his personality, and psychologically the people are more wiser than this aphorism [“actions speak louder than words”], when the will or involuntarily pays a lot of attention to the psychological significance of language human” (Sapir, 1993b, p. 234).

Leonard Bloomfield, who came to America in 1868 from the Polish city of Bilica, was born in Chicago (1887–1949) into an Austro-Jewish family. His uncle, Maurice Bloomfield (1855-1928), was a well-known American linguist and the second president of the Linguistic Society of America. He spent much of his career giving lectures on comparative philology and Sanskrit at Johns Hopkins University. Bloomfield continued to research the Algonquian languages and the Malayo-Polynesian languages while serving as an emeritus professor of linguistics at Yale University from 1940 until 1949.

During the war, Bloomfield actively participated in the creation of a unique foreign language instruction program for military troops. He wrote a tiny brochure. “Guide to the practical study of foreign languages” (1942), a short textbook on Russian language “Conversational Russian” (1944). The reviews of Bloomfield as a man of his generation are particularly interesting. Bloch wrote: "His personality was not especially appealing. He was too modest to impose his convictions on others who are too withdrawn to find satisfaction in overpowering the audience." (Bloch, 1966, p. 514). Knew well Bloomfield R. Hall (Jr.) (1911-1998) said: “He was very calm, timid, reserved. On rare occasions, he raised his voice, and his speech often gave the listener the feeling that he was extremely timid and hesitant[10.90].

Unlike the natural sciences, linguistics relies on small, dynamic groups of individuals that comprise a speech community for its purpose. combinations of morphemes and phonemes that are socially ingrained in the society and signify reactions to outside stimuli (meaning).

Both primitive and developed humans have the same lexicon and structure. According to Bloomfield, linguistics distinguishes between more and less prevalent forms of human speech. Linguistics does not share this distinction with philology. The field of linguistics emphasizes that it cannot be viewed as a subset of philology. According to him, the problems with American education are that teachers are ignorant of the advances made in linguistics, the differences between written and spoken language, and the relationship between literary and dialectal languages. [2.67].

Conclusion

To conclude today studying the history of the development of linguistics is an important task. Moreover, by translating the scientific heritage of great linguists such as Edward Sapir, Franz Boas, Leonard Bloomfield, Noam Chomsky we implement a significant source for younger generation. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated, "Science and enlightenment are important in increasing the intellectual and spiritual capabilities of not only young people, but also our entire society." Therefore, scientific research is one of the basic sources of the country's development, and the field of linguistics is no exception.

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ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 3

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